

TRACING THE TRACE: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF IMPURITY PROFILING IN ATORVASTATIN CALCIUM AND BEMPEDOIC ACID

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ABSTRACT

This evaluation includes some impurity data regarding bempedoic acid and atorvastatin calcium, two authorised anti-cholesteremic medications. Contamination, toxicity, and the production of hazardous compounds can result from impurities in the drug's formulation and bulk. As a result, pollutants reduce the need for APIs and diminish their safety and effectiveness. This includes details on several topics, including limits, sources, terminology, and structural figures. Additionally, pharmacopoeias are beginning to establish reporting criteria and thresholds for certain API pollutants, and regulatory bodies such as the ICH have strict. Because of this, it is easier to identify and discover the undesirable or generated components during the process thanks to the impurity information. Therefore, this review lists a variety of contaminants that may be found in atorvastatin calcium API and bempedoic acid, or that may be synthesised during the process, originating from raw materials, produced during storage, or degraded over time. It also indicates the potentiality of these contaminants based on the range of consumption.

Keywords: *Bempedoic acid, Atorvastatin, Impurity profiling*

1. INTRODUCTION

A vast range of drugs, chemicals, and other materials that are utilised in formulations are encountered in the pharmaceutical industry. These drugs, substances, or materials are produced synthetically or from scratch. In terms of drug substances and drug products, any extraneous material found with API in bulk drugs—whether it comes from raw materials, happens during an intermediate process or happens post-manufacturing is regarded as an impurity. Conversely, impurity profiling identifies the types of contaminants that are present (both known and unknown), isolation, and structural elucidation and degradation products in bulk or formulations. The limits of contaminants are also included in pharmacopoeias for pure medications and their commercial formulations [1-4]. The ICH and other regulatory bodies' guidelines classify impurities together with their threshold and other relevant information. As, the need for the product to be as pure as possible, however, never goes away. The ICH impurity guidelines for new drug products classify them as reaction or degradation products that occur during manufacturing while standards for new drug substances mainly focus on safety and chemical issues, they also classify impurities into the following categories: [5-8]

(i) Organic impurities: These result from the material's handling during production and storage. These could be vaporizable or non-vaporizable, known or unknown. Feedstocks, end products, molecules produced during synthesis, products produced after degradation, chemicals, ligands, and components initiating the synthesis process are a few examples of these.

(ii) Inorganic impurities: It is commonly known that during the production process, inorganic impurities may occur. Among these are inorganic salts, reagents, catalysts, and heavy-metal, ligands.

(iii) Residual solvents: These are employed in the synthesis procedure.

Sources of impurities: These include crystallisation, stereochemistry, residual solvent, synthetic intermediates and by-products, formulation-related, emerging during storage, method-related, interactions among ingredients, chemical group-associated degradation, and so forth [4].

Table 1: Limit of impurities for drug substance

Category	Impurity threshold	
Maximum daily consumption (In g)	$\geq 2g$	$\leq 2g$
Reporting (In %)	0.03	0.05
Identification (In %)	0.05	0.10
Qualification (In %)	0.05	0.15

Table 2. Limit of impurities for drug products

Category		Degradation product threshold					
Maximum daily intake	In g	<0.001	0.001-0.01	>0.01-0.1	>0.1-1	>1-2	>2
Reporting	In %	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.05
Identification	%	1	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1
	mg TDI*	0.005	0.02	2	2	2	-
Qualification	%	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.15
	mg TDI*	0.05	0.05	0.2	3	3	-

TDI*= Total Daily Intake

1.1 Atorvastatin calcium

It is a whitish to off-white, crystal-like powder that belongs to a member of the statin class. This anti-cholesteric drug inhibits the enzyme HMG Co-A reductase, preventing HMG Co-A from being converted to mevalonate. IUPAC name for calcium; 7- [2-(4-fluorophenyl) -3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbomoyl)-5-propan-2-ylpyrrol-1-yl] 3,5-dihydroxyheptanoate with a molecular mass of 1155.3 g/mol [9]. A variety of Atorvastatin impurities can arise during synthesis, degradation, stability-related issues and many more.

Figure 1. Structure of Atorvastatin calcium

Where,

(1) Phenylacetic acid; (2) Phenyl acetyl chloride; (3) Fluorobenzene; (4) Benzyl-4-fluorophenyl ethanone; (5) 2-chloro-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-phenylethanone; (6) Aniline; (7) Methyl isobutyrylacetate; (8) 4-methyl-3-oxo-n-phenylpentanamide; (9) 2-(2-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxo-1-phenylethyl)-4-methyl-3-oxo-n-phenylpentanamide; (10) Tert-butyl 2-((4R,6R)-6-(2-aminoethyl)-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxan-4-yl)acetate; (11) Atorvastatin calcium

Figure 2. Synthesis of Atorvastatin calcium [10]**Table 3.** Atorvastatin impurities originating from or existing in bulk medications and commercial formulations based on pharmacopoeias and non-pharmacopoeias [11-21]

Sr. no.	Impurity	Impurity name	Structure	Description
Potential impurities				
1.	A/ desfluoro	(3R,5R)-3,5-dihydroxy-7-[2-(1-methylethyl)-4,5-diphenyl-3-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]heptanoic acid calcium salt(2:1)		Molecular mass: C ₆₆ H ₇₀ CaN ₄ O ₁₀ Molecular formula: 1118.47 g/mol Cause of impurity: Process related Limit of impurity: 0.3%
2.	B/ (3S,5R)	(3S,5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-phenylcarbamoyl]-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid calcium salt(2:1)		Molecular mass: 1155.34 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₆₆ H ₆₈ CaF ₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cause of impurity: Process related Limit of impurity: 0.3%

3.	C/ difluo ro	(3R,5R)-7-[2,3-bis(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid		Molecular mass: 1191.34 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₆₆ H ₆₆ F ₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cause of impurity: Process related Limit of impurity: 0.3%
4.	D/ epoxy - dione	3-(4-fluorobenzoyl)-2-(2-methylpropanoyl)-N,3-diphenyl oxirane-2-carboxamide		Molecular mass: 431.46 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₆ H ₂₂ FNO ₄ Cause of impurity: Degradation product (oxidative, photolytic) Limit of impurity: 0.15%
5.	E/ (3S, 5S)	(3S,5S)-7-(2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-isopropyl-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl)-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoate calcium salt		Molecular mass: 1155.34 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₆₆ H ₆₈ CaF ₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cause of impurity: Process related Limit of impurity: 0.3%
6.	F/ diami no	7-[[7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methyl ethyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoyl]amino-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid		Molecular mass: 717.82 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₄₀ H ₄₈ FN ₃ O ₈ Cause of impurity: Process related Limit of impurity: 0.1%
7.	G/ o- meth yl ATR	(3R,5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-5-hydroxy-3-methoxyheptanoic acid calcium salt(2:1)		Molecular mass: 572.67 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₄ H ₃₆ FN ₂ O ₅ Cause of impurity: Process-related Limit of impurity: 0.1%
8.	H/ lacton e	5-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-[2-(4-hydroxy-6-oxooxan-2-yl)ethyl]-N-4-diphenyl-2-propan-2-ylpyrrole-3-carboxamide		Molecular mass: 540.62 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₃ FN ₂ O ₄ Cause of impurity: synthesis, Degradation product (acid hydrolysis, thermal) Limit of impurity: 0.15%
9.	I/ aceto nide t- butyl ester	Tert-butyl-[(4R,6R)-6-{2-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]ethyl}-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxan-4-yl]acetate		Molecular mass: 654.81 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₄₀ H ₄₇ FN ₂ O ₅ Cause of impurity: intermediate Limit of impurity: 0.15%

10.	J/ 3- deoxy hept- 2- enoic acid	(2E,5S)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-5-hydroxyhept-2-enoic acid		Molecular mass: 540.24 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₃ FN ₂ O ₄ Cause of impurity: synthesis related, Degradation product (acid hydrolysis, thermal, photolytic)
11.	K/ ethyl ester	Ethyl(3R,5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoate		Limit of impurity: 0.1% Molecular mass: 572.67 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₄ H ₃₇ FN ₂ O ₅ Limit of impurity: 0.15%
12.	L/ epoxy tetrahydrofuran analog	4-(4-fluorophenyl)-2,4-dihydroxy-2-(1-methylethyl)-N,5-diphenyl-3,6-dioxabicyclo[3.1.0]hexane-1-carboxamide		Molecular mass: 449.47 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₆ H ₂₄ FN ₂ O ₅ Cause of impurity: Degradation product (Oxidative, photolytic)
13.	M/ tert-butyl ester	Tert-butyl(3R,5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoate		Limit of impurity: 0.15% Molecular mass: 614.76 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₇ H ₄₃ FN ₂ O ₅ Cause of impurity: synthesis related
14.	N	(3R,5R)-7-[3-(phenylcarbamoyl)-5-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-isopropyl-4-phenyl-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid tert-butyl ester		Molecular mass: 614.76 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₇ H ₄₃ FN ₂ O ₅ Cause of impurity: intermediates
15.	O/ 3-oxo ATR	(5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-5-(1-methylethyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-5-hydroxy-3-oxoheptanoic acid calcium		Molecular mass: 1151.31 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₆₆ H ₆₄ CaFN ₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cause of impurity: synthesis related
16.	P/ Acetone	(4R-cis)-6-{2-[[2-(4-fluorophenyl)]-5-(1-methylethyl)-3-phenyl-4-[(phenylamino) carbonyl]-1H-pyrrole-2-yl]ethyl}-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxane-4-acetic acid diisopropyl amine salt		Molecular mass: 699.89 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₆ H ₃₉ FN ₂ O ₅ Cause of impurity: organic Impurity limit: 0.05%

17.	Q	(3R,5R)-7-[5-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxo-4-phenyl-3-(phenylcarbamoyl)-3-(propan-2-yl)-2,3-dihydro-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid		Molecular mass: 574.64 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₅ FN ₂ O ₆ Cause of impurity: intermediates
18.	Diamino impurity	(3R,5R)-7-[(3R,5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-isopropyl-3-(phenylcarbamoyl)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptamido]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid		Molecular mass: 854.06 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₅₀ H ₆₄ FN ₃ O ₈ Cause of impurity: process related Limit of impurity: 0.15%
Degradation products				
19.	FX1	(3R)-4-1b-(4-fluorophenyl)-7-hydroxy-7-isopropyl-1a-phenyl-7a-(phenylcarbamoyl)hexahydro-3H-oxireno[3,4]pyrrolo[2,1-b][1,3]oxazin-3-yl)-3-hydroxybutanoic acid sodium		Molecular mass: 612.62 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₄ FN ₂ NaO ₇ Cause of impurity: degradation (oxidative)
20.	Epoxy pyrralooxazin 6-hydroxy analog	4-{6-(4-fluorophenyl)-7,8-epoxy-6-hydroxy-8a-isopropyl-7-phenyl-8-(phenylcarbamoyl)hexahydro-2H-pyrrolo[2,1-b][1,3]oxazin-2-yl}-3-hydroxybutanoic acid sodium		Molecular mass: 612.62 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₄ FN ₂ NaO ₇ Cause of impurity: degradation
21.	FXA/6-hydroxy analog	(3R)-4-[7-(4-fluorophenyl)-7-hydroxy-1b-(1-methylethyl)-7a-phenyl-1a-(phenylcarbamoyl)-hexahydro-3H-oxireno[3,4]pyrrolo[2,1-b][1,3]oxazin-3-yl]-3-hydroxybutanoic acid		Molecular mass: 590.64 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₅ FN ₂ O ₇ Cause of impurity: degradation (oxidative)
22.	FXA1/Dehydrate lactone	5-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-(1-methyl ethyl)-1-{2-[(2S)-6-oxo-3,6-dihydro-2H-pyran-2-yl]ethyl}-N,4-diphenyl-1H-pyrrol-3-carboxamide		Molecular mass: 522.61 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₁ FN ₂ O ₃ Cause of impurity: degradation (photo-oxidation)
23.,	Lactam sodium salt	(3R,5R)-7-[5-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-(phenylcarbamoyl)-3-(propan-2-yl)pyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoate sodium		Molecular mass: 596.62 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₃ H ₃₄ FN ₂ NaO ₆ Cause of impurity: degradation (photolytic)

24.	FXA 2/epoxy tetrahydrofuran	4-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-(1-methyl ethyl)-N,2-diphenyl-5-[2(tetrahydro-4-hydroxy-6-oxo-2H-pyran-2-yl)ethyl]-3,7-dioxo-5-azatricyclo[4.1.0.0.2,4]heptanes-1-carboxamide		Molecular mass: 449.47 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₆ H ₂₄ FNO ₅ Cause of impurity: degradation (photolytic)
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1.2 Bempeidic acid

This prodrug has an IUPAC name of 8-hydroxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethylpentadecanedioic acid and is a whitish to off-white colour powder with a molecular mass of 344.49 g/mol. This BCS class II member first transforms into the active form, bempedoil co-a, and subsequently prevents ATP citrate lyase from converting to acetyl co-a, which functions as an ACL inhibitor [22].

Figure 3. Structure of Bempeidic acid

Where,

(1) 1,5 dibromopentane; (2) Ethylisobutyrate; (3) Ethyl-7-bromo-2,2dimethylheptanoate; (4) tosylmethylisocyanide; (5) Diethyl 8-isocyano-2,2,14,14 tetramethyl-8-tosylpentadecanedioate; (6) Diethyl ester-2,2,14,14,-tetramethyl-8-oxopentadecanedioic acid; (7) 2,2,14,14 tetramethyl-8-oxopentadecanedioic acid; (8) Bempeidic acid;

Figure 4. Synthesis of Bempedoic acid [23]**Table 4.** Bempedoic acid impurities originating from or existing in bulk and commercial formulations based on pharmacopoeias and non-pharmacopoeias [24-27]

Sr. No.	Impurity name	Structure	Description
1.	2,2,14,14 tetramethyl-8-oxo pentadecandioic acid		Molecular mass: 342.48 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₅
2.	Diethyl 8-cyano 2,2,14,14 tetramethyl-8-tosyl pentadecandioic acid		Molecular mass: 563.79 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₁ H ₄₉ NO ₆ S
3.	8,14-dihydroxy-2,2,20,20-tetramethylhenicosanedioic acid		Molecular mass: 444.65 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₅ H ₄₈ O ₆
4.	3,3 diethyl- 2,2,14,14 tetramethyl-8-oxopentadecandioic acid		Molecular mass: 398.58 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₃ H ₄₂ O ₅
5.	8-((14-carboxy-8-hydroxy-2,2,14-trimethylpentadecanoyl)oxy)-2,2,14,14-tetramethylpentadecanedioic acid		Molecular mass: 670.97 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₈ H ₇₀ O ₉
6.	2,2,8,8-tetramethylnonanedioic acid		Molecular mass: 244.33 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₁₃ H ₂₄ O ₄
7.	Diethyl-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl-8-oxopentadecanedioate		Molecular mass: 398.58 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₃ H ₄₂ O ₅
8.	Diethyl-8-hydroxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethylpentadecadioate		Molecular mass: 400.6 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₃ H ₄₄ O ₅
9.	15-ethoxy-8-hydroxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl-15-oxopentadecanoic acid		Molecular mass: C ₂₁ H ₄₀ O ₅ g/mol Molecular formula: 372.55 g/mol
10.	15-ethoxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl-8,15-dioxopentadecanoic acid		Molecular mass: 370.53 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₁ H ₃₈ O ₅

11.	3-cyano-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl-8-oxopentadecanedioic acid		Molecular mass: 369.50 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₀ H ₃₅ NO ₅
12.	Ethyl 7-bromo-2,2-dimethylheptanoate		Molecular mass: 265.19 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₁₁ H ₂₁ BrO ₂
13.	7-bromo-2,2-dimethylheptanoic acid		Molecular mass: 237.14 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₉ H ₁₇ BrO ₂
14.	Diethyl 8-isocyano-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl-8-tosyl pentadecanoic acid		Molecular mass: 563..79 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₃₁ H ₄₉ NO ₆ S
15.	Dimethyl-8-hydroxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethylpentadecandioate		Molecular mass: 372.55 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₁ H ₄₀ O ₅
16.	8-acetoxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl pentadecanoic acid		Molecular mass: 386.53 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₁ H ₃₈ O ₆
17.	8-hydroxy-15-methoxy-2,2,14,14-tetramethyl-15-oxopentadecanoic acid		Molecular mass: 358.52 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₅
18.	(2S,3S,4S,5R,6S)-6-((14-carboxy-8-hydroxy-2,2,14-tetramethylpentadecanoyl)oxy)-3,4,5-trihydroxytetrahydro-2H-pyran-2-carboxylic acid		Molecular mass: 520.62 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₅ H ₄₄ O ₁₁
19.	8-(formyl oxy)-2,2,14,14-tetramethylpentadecanedioic acid		Molecular mass: 372.5 g/mol Molecular formula: C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O ₆

2. CONCLUSION

While research on the causes and limits of Bempedoic acid's predicted impurities is still ongoing, information about Atorvastatin's impurities has come from pharmacopoeias and research articles. Stated differently, a thorough investigation of the impurity in Bempedoic acid and Atorvastatin calcium reveals a complicated terrain. It is imperative to analyse and characterise these known or unknown impurities to improve and preserve the medication and drug product quality, safety, and efficacy. This will enable continuous improvement and guarantee the pharmaceutical quality of these vital medications.

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